
The Essence of the Concept of Quality in Hotels and The Objective Need to Ensure it

Mir-Jafarova Aziza Javahirovna

SamIES, assistant of the department of "Tourism"

***Abstract.** Further development of the service sector in our republic with the formation and deepening of market relations, creating a competitive environment in it, in the current complex conditions, puts various new and extremely important issues on the agenda. Among them, the issue of improving the quality and efficiency of hotel services in the field of tourism is very important.*

***Keywords:** quality, service, motel, hotel, guestroom.*

INTRODUCTION

There are different approaches to the interpretation of the concept of "quality of service". ISO 8402-94 "Quality management and assurance. The definition given in the international standard "Dictionary" is especially widely used: "Service quality is a set of characteristics of a service that ensure its ability to meet specified or anticipated needs." In the international standard ISO 8402-94, the term "service quality" is also adopted, and it is considered as a set of specific characteristics and conditions of the service process that allow satisfying the identified or estimated needs of the consumer. The most important features of the service that ensure the ability to meet specific needs include:

- reliability;
- enthusiasm;
- reliability;
- promptness;
- communicativeness;
- courtesy.

Reliability refers to the ability of employees to deliver the promised service accurately. Developing a quality service program must begin with ensuring reliability. The high level of professionalism of service personnel is the basis for ensuring reliability. The damage to the reputation of the hotel as a result of the incompetence of the staff cannot be smoothed over by the huge expenses spent on the reconstruction and re-equipment of the hotel building, as well as by the friendly and courteous attitude to the client.

Enthusiasm - readiness to help the customer and provide prompt service. During service, emergencies often occur or customers make unexpected requests (for example, to put a white grand piano in the

room or a bigger bed, etc.). In such cases, the company's ability to find a reasonable solution to the problem is assessed.

The peculiarity of the activities of enterprises in the field of services, in particular, hotel services, is that emergency situations have always occurred here. Therefore, it is necessary to plan ways to solve such problems in advance and develop your own work principles. In such cases, employees should work with quality, pay immediate attention to the problems that arise, and follow the principles of working with demanding and quarrelsome customers of every enterprise (according to the Pareto rule, it can be estimated that 20% of customers cause 80% of problems).

There are many scientific works devoted to quality management, in which the concept of "service quality" is interpreted and defined differently, but in each of them, the orientation of services to the consumer has the main place.

According to N.Yu.Arbusova, the quality of hotel services is a set of properties and definition of certain services, which are defined properties or perhaps waiting and means to give the feature of satisfying the requirements.

The following situation is not taken into account:

- improving the quality of services is always associated with an increase in costs to achieve additional features of services:
- the guest receives high-quality services at a high price.

In this case, the financial capabilities of hotels come first. It should also be taken into account that the quality of services in hotels of different categories is different.

R. Brymer shows that the quality of services provided in accordance with the standards of the hotel business is of a certain type, they are confirmed by a firm, corporation, association or a single network, even a small deviation from the norms means that there is no quality.

In practice, there are examples of high-quality hotel services, if they are aimed at meeting all the needs of guests, regardless of standards. This situation is not taken into account in this definition. It should be noted that currently there is no unified understanding among many authors regarding the category of hotel service quality, in particular, as an object of management.

In our opinion, the quality of hotel services is a certain set of standards and a variety of services that customers expect to receive. meals, various additional and auxiliary services, provide satisfaction of individual needs of customers defined in practice. From this point of view, quality has normative properties defined in relevant standards, quality can be compared only among similar services, quality can be evaluated by each consumer based on socio-economic parameters and his personal preferences.

Hotel services have a number of unique features, knowing them and organizing and managing services on this basis allows to increase the quality and efficiency of hotel services and income. These and many other aspects are known to most professionals and depend mainly on the following characteristics of hotel services:

- 1). Simultaneous occurrence of production and consumption processes of services and products. The provision of hotel services requires the active participation of both the consumer and the performer, such services take place on the territory of the performer. The service employee is in direct contact with the consumer, and the consumer considers the executive employee to be an integral part of the hotel

service. The quality of hotel services is largely evaluated by the guest depending on the behavior of the employee;

2) Insensitivity. Hotel service is unlike any other service. Services are intangible, they cannot be evaluated until they are consumed, they exist only in the process of service provision and consumption;

3) The impossibility of storing, collecting and storing the product (service) produced by the hotel. The hotel product is designed to meet current consumption. If the services are not provided on time and with good quality, the hotel's revenue opportunities will be lost and they will not be restored;

4) Change of quality (non-permanence). The hospitality industry is characterized by variability, the quality of which depends on who provides the service and under what conditions. The condition of the service provider at the time of service can have a strong impact on the quality of the service. A single person can provide excellent customer service today and very poor customer service tomorrow for any number of reasons (e.g. bad mood, family problems, etc.). The variability and fluctuation of the quality of the provided service are the main reasons for the dissatisfaction expressed by customers in the name of the hotel industry;

5) Seasonality of demand and need. Hotel services are subject to seasonal fluctuations. Demand and demand for hotel products (accommodation and other services) can fluctuate daily, weekly or seasonally. For example, most tourists are on vacation in the summer, and accordingly, the demand for hotel services increases significantly during this period;

6) Interdependence of hotel services and travel (visit) purposes. The actions of tour operators and travel agents have a great impact on the sale of hotel products, because the hotel business is closely related to tourist activity;

7) The volume of sales of hotel services depends on a number of factors: the location of the hotel; ease of service; service level and variety; hotel image; rates and prices; range of services, etc.

Credibility is the ability of employees to instill confidence in themselves. It is important to pay attention to the external cues that consumers trust most in order to create a relationship of mutual trust. The hotel interior, numbers, well-organized interior of the restaurant, cleanliness of the rooms, corridors, friendly appearance of the staff - all these are external criteria of the quality of service, and customers know that everything is in order in a particular enterprise and that it can be trusted. makes a conclusion based on.

Speed - ease of communication with service personnel. For example, if the guest called the driver to the number, he should arrive not in a few hours, but in a few minutes. 217 Communicativeness - provision of service that excludes misunderstandings between employees and customers due to providing necessary information to customers on time and without their additional request.

Courtesy - paying special attention to the client and providing him with individual service. Each customer has their own specific needs. In order to ensure that the client remains loyal to the enterprise, it is necessary to show that a particular client is of special importance for the enterprise and that his individual needs are taken into account during the provision of services. When considering the quality of services, non-standard definitions such as "meets demand - does not meet", "above - below demand level", "good - bad", "meets demand - does not meet" are often used. For example: "The quality of service in local hotels does not meet the requirements of international standards", the level of service in

the "Dostlik" hotel is lower than the level of service in a three-star hotel", "The quality of services provided in hotels in small cities" can be evaluated as "unsatisfactory".

The prevalence of non-standard terms in relation to the quality of services is reasonable, because it allows to show the variety of quality characteristics of the hospitality enterprises.

What the target consumer understands by quality in the service market is important for hospitality enterprises, that is, when discussing the concept of "quality", the personality of the consumer is in focus. When evaluating the quality of the service, the consumer compares what he has been given to what he wants to receive. The assessment given to a particular service depends on the consumer's experience of applying to enterprises providing such services, knowledge about the service, personal preferences, and the image of the enterprise providing the service. The service used is subject to the effects of selective reception, adaptation and amplification. Selective acceptance means that the same service is accepted differently by different consumers. This is determined by the character, interests, personal qualities, knowledge of consumers, as well as the state of using the service.

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